

Standalone Applications for Major Depressive Disorders: A Systematic Review

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Introduction: Standalone mobile health (mHealth) applications have been increasingly adopted as accessible digital health interventions (DHIs) to support early detection and the self-management of depressive disorders¹⁼³. However, the extent to which the components of these DHIs translate into consistent clinical benefits remains uncertain⁴⁻⁵. This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of automated app-based interventions in reducing depressive symptom severity among adults and to analyze their therapeutic and technological components.

Methods: A systematic review and aggregated analysis of randomized clinical trials (RCTs) were conducted in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines⁶. Searches were performed in PubMed, Embase, and the Cochrane Library. Eligible studies were those that included app-based digital interventions for adults with depressive symptoms, assessed using the Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9) according to Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-IV.)⁷ All included trials were fully automated self-help interventions with minimal or no human support⁸. Each intervention was characterized according to the presence of key design features, including the use of cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) approaches⁹, gamification strategies¹⁰, conversational elements, and artificial intelligence (AI) functionalities. Discrepancies were resolved by arriving at a consensus between authors.

Results: Seventeen RCTs¹¹⁻²⁷ met the inclusion criteria. Studies were conducted across multiple geographic regions and exhibited substantial variability in sample size, participant characteristics, population specificity, and scale-based measures, as detailed in Table 1. Participants generally presented with mild to moderate depressive symptom severity, and samples were predominantly female. Most studies were conducted in high-income countries. Four^{15,20,21,25} did not report sufficient data (mean and standard deviation values) to be included in the quantitative synthesis, as shown in Figure 1. Substantial statistical heterogeneity ($I^2 = 84.3\%$) was observed. The aggregated analysis demonstrated a statistically significant reduction in depressive symptom severity, favoring standalone mHealth interventions, with a pooled effect estimate of -1.83 (95% confidence interval -2.71 to -0.94; $p = 0.0007$). Individual effect sizes varied considerably, ranging from large reductions in PHQ-9 scores to modest or non-significant effects, reflecting differences in intervention design, duration, and population characteristics. Among DHIs, CBT was the most frequently adopted therapeutic framework.

Gamification elements were the second most common feature, followed by conversational components and AI-based functionalities.

Discussion: mHealth interventions represent one of the most prevalent categories among DHIs, largely due to their adaptability across diverse populations and settings²⁸. The findings suggest a potential positive impact on the treatment of depressive disorders. However, interpretation of these results is influenced by methodological constraints and heterogeneity in intervention design.

Methodologically, small sample sizes, predominantly female samples, and reliance on passive comparators are important factors contributing to heterogeneity across studies, substantially compromising external validity²⁹. Additionally, the exclusion of severe cases is clinically appropriate and ethically justified for safety reasons²⁸; however, it restricts the applicability of findings primarily to mild-to-moderate presentations.

Regarding theoretical foundations, interventions were grounded primarily in CBT frameworks and delivered through diverse mobile formats, including chatbots, mini-apps, and messaging systems. Effect sizes varied considerably, with gamified or AI-based apps reporting substantially greater effects than minimally guided interventions, suggesting that the degree of therapeutic structure and interactivity may influence clinical outcomes. This is further supported by a large-scale trial¹² showing that behavioral activation outperformed cognitive restructuring, indicating that not all CBT components contribute equally to symptom reduction.

From an implementation perspective, Brazil's Digital Health Strategy 2020-2028 emphasizes the integration of mobile platforms into the Public Health System³⁰. However, adapting digital tools for vulnerable populations remains challenging, as demonstrated by a Brazilian trial in which a messaging-based intervention for older adults in economically disadvantaged areas did not significantly reduce depressive symptoms¹⁹.

Future studies should prioritize active comparators, longer follow-up periods, and more targeted populations to better identify the intervention components most strongly associated with clinical benefits.

Conclusion: Standalone mHealth interventions showed a statistically significant reduction in depressive symptom severity among adults with mild-to-moderate presentations. However, methodological heterogeneity limits the generalizability of these findings. Further robust multicentric studies with stricter methodological standards are needed to establish evidence-based guidelines for mHealth development.

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Supplementary material

Study, Year (Country)	Participants (N) / Female (%)	Mean age (SD)	Population Specificity	Scale-based inclusion criteria	Mobile Intervention
Bae, 2024 (South Korea) ¹¹	N=39; 51.2%	62.1 (NR)	Type 2 diabetes; low-income group	PHQ-9 5–19	DangDang Care
Bruhns, 2021 (USA) ¹²	N=400; 88.5%	22.98 (3.36)	MDD symptoms	PHQ-9 > 0; item 9 ≤ 1	MCT & More
Cox, 2019 (Chile) ¹³	N=80; 44%	49.5 (15.1)	MDD, GAD, PTSD; post-critical illness	NR	NR
Fulmer, 2018 (USA) ¹⁴	N=74; 70%	22.9 (NR)	MDD and GAD	Self-identified depression/anxiety	Tess
Furukawa, 2025 (Japan) ¹⁵	N=3,936; 49%	43.1 (10.7)	Subthreshold depression	PHQ-9 5–14; item 9 ≤ 1	Resilience Training
Kim, 2025 (South Korea) ¹⁶	N=170; 80%	22.60 (3.37)	MDD; college students	PHQ-9 ≥ 5; item 9 ≤ 1	Mind Booster Green
Li, 2024 (Canada) ¹⁷	N=49; 59%	41.0 (13.9)	MDD; bipolar depression	DSM-5 MDE; QIDS-SR ≥ 10	MoodFX
Lukas, 2021 (Germany) ¹⁸	N=77; 72.2%	29.93 (11.61)	MDD	PHQ-9 ≥ 5	Mentalis Phoenix
Nakamura, 2023 (Brazil) ¹⁹	N=292; 64%	65.3 (5.0)	MDD symptoms; socioeconomically deprived regions	PHQ-2 ≥ 1; PHQ-9 5–9	Viva Vida (via WhatsApp Application)
Sanatkar, 2025 (Australia) ²⁰	N=781; 74.14%	30.5 (5.1)	MDD symptoms; doctors in training	NR	Shift mHealth
Shao, 2025 (China) ²¹	N=223; 40%	25.7 (5.5)	MDD and GAD	PHQ-9 ≥ 10; GAD-7 ≥ 8	NR
Tan, 2023 (Malaysia) ²²	N=37; 77%	32.9 (12.5)	MDD and GAD	PHQ-9 ≥ 5 and <15; GAD-7 ≥ 5 and <15	MoodMission
Wong, 2021 (China) ²³	N=79; 84.8%	32.9 (12.5)	MDD	PHQ-9 ≥ 10	Lifestyle Hub
Xu, 2025 (China) ²⁴	N=84; 48.8%	23.3 (1.07)	MDD and GAD	PHQ-9 ≥ 9	Neil
Yatziv, 2024 (USA) ²⁵	N=117; 77.8%	32.43 (8.5)	MDD	MADRS ≥ 15 and < 35	MoodVille
Yokomitsu, 2025 (Japan) ²⁶	N=73; 63%	40.4 (10.7)	MDD and GAD	PHQ-9 10–27	Intellect
Zhao, 2025 (China) ²⁷	N=657; 61.8%	20.59 (2.00)	MDD and GAD	PHQ-9 ≥ 5; GAD-7 ≥ 5	Douyin Xinqing

Table 1: Characteristics of included randomized controlled trials evaluating mobile health interventions for depressive symptoms of all studies (N = 17).

Abbreviations: GAD-7, Generalized Anxiety Disorder-7; MADRS, Montgomery-Åsberg Depression Rating Scale; MDD, major depressive disorder; NR, not reported; PHQ-9, Patient Health Questionnaire-9; PTSD, post-traumatic stress disorder; QIDS-SR, Quick Inventory of Depressive Symptomatology–Self-Report; SD, standard deviation.

Figure 1: Forest plot of mean differences in PHQ-9 scores. Studies are ordered by effect size, from largest to smallest reductions. Only trials reporting mean and standard deviation were included (N = 13).